

HadISDH.marine Update Document

Kate Willett (MOHC), 8th March 2022

General Notes:

The HadISDH.marine.1.3.0.2021f contains all 12 months of 2021. There are no major changes (X). There is a minor code change from Python 2.7 to Python 3 and the climatological reference period has changed from 1981-2010 to 1991-2020, in line with WMO recommendations. This warrants a full re-run of the data processing and an increment of the Y version number. There are no historical changes, or bug fixes. Keep up to date with subsequent changes and analyses at <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2022/03/2021-update-from-hadisdhmarinev1302021f.html>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

1.3.0.2021f

Major Changes X:

- None

Minor Changes Y:

- The climatological reference period has changed from 1981-2010 to 1991-2020. Observation inclusion depends on a climatological value being available for that grid point (1 by 1 degree pentad [5 day average]) so this will change the coverage slightly. It also affects any quality control that uses the climatological mean or standard deviation such as the outlier check. Additionally, the remaining Python 2.7 code has been updated to Python 3.

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

- None

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2021-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): URL: <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1477>

Reference: No change

Other notes: The HadISDH update/analyses blog is here:

<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2022/03/2021-update-from-hadisdhmarinev1302021f.html>